

Various Programs

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Overview

Tools for *calculations, bootstrapping* and *permutation tests*, also for *practice* purposes when learning programming languages (C, Basic, Fortran etc.), see e.g. Halvorson and Rygmyr (1991), Chivers and Sleightholme (2018), Joyce (2019), Streib (2020) or Gonzalez-Morris and Horton (2024):

i. Tools, also for practice purposes:

FAC, IINORMAL, LD, MC1, MCDAT, MCSPS, MO, PROBE, PSX (c.f. Schrausser, 2023a), *RAN, RECHTECK, RN, SHIFT, T, Z, ZP, CWN-DW, TAGE, ascii_1, asciiode, asciiode_1, sigma01, sigma02sim*.

ii. Mathematics:

Potenzen, deconv, NI, winkel, fx_euler, sinus_sum, kugeloberflaeche, kugelraum_1, kugelvolumen, kugelvolumen_n1, kugelvolumen_n2, tetra1, tetra_alg1, tetra_alg2, tetra_h, tetra_h1, tetra_o, tetra_s, tetrah, tetrah1, tetrao, tetrao1, tetrav, tetrav1, z00, z001.

iii. Bootstrapping and permutation tests:

*PITMAN, STAT-SAK*¹ (s. Dallal, 1986, 1988), *BOOTSTRA, GROUPEFUN, KSBLKS, KSMIN, RANDPERM, RPM, PERMT4* (c.f. Schrausser, 2025a, b, res.).

iv. Utilities etc.:

CAD, CUT, DICE (see Schrausser, 2023b, c), *GAME, GRAPH, TXWND, GR_0041, rotation_004, rndn, rnd2, GSW, Graph, Mondphasen_021c, Mondrotation_01, colorscreen*.

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poses is permitted, without charge, provided that suitable reference is made to PC-PITMAN or STAT-SAK and its author.